

The REVERTER project White Paper Digital One-Stop Shops for Tackling Energy Poverty in Europe

“Lessons learned, results and recommendations from pilot implementations in Latvia, Greece, Bulgaria and Portugal”

Prepared by Linda Kimeiša, Guna Valtere, WIT Berry

Date October, 2025

Co-funded by
the European Union

Funded by the LIFE Programme of the European
Union, Grant Agreement No. 101076277

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Executive summary

Project REVERTER aims to tackle energy poverty (EP) by addressing the root causes of inefficient housing, limited access to renovation resources, and low awareness among vulnerable populations. Funded under the LIFE Programme (No 101076277), REVERTER seeks to improve energy efficiency across Europe through the development of targeted renovation roadmaps, focusing on the "worst first" principle—prioritizing the most inefficient buildings and the most vulnerable households.

One of the important objectives of the REVERTER project is the conceptualization, development, and maintenance of four **Digital One-Stop Shops (DOSS)** — comprehensive, user-friendly platforms tailored to the local contexts of citizens in **Latvia, Greece, Bulgaria, and Portugal**.

These platforms act as primary access points for vulnerable households seeking guidance, financial assistance, technical information and expert support for home renovation projects. While designed with vulnerable groups in mind, DOSS are accessible to all citizens, ensuring that everyone can easily find relevant information. Broad engagement also fosters knowledge sharing across communities — amplifying awareness through word-of-mouth and collective action.

This white paper presents the rationale, design, and implementation of DOSS within the REVERTER framework. It explores how these digital solutions address market, behavioural, and informational barriers that often discourage low-income households from undertaking energy renovations. By integrating local languages, climate conditions, policy environments, and user-centered design principles, each DOSS provides scalable and cost-effective renovation pathways aligned with EU energy and climate objectives.

By embedding its findings into national and EU-level policies, REVERTER aims to achieve lasting impact, advance energy equity, and contribute to the broader goals of the European Green Deal and Clean Energy for All Europeans.

Finally, this paper offers an in-depth overview of how DOSS are being designed, adapted, and implemented across the four pilot countries — providing practical insights, lessons learned, and early outcomes that can inform future replication across Europe.

1. Introduction

Energy efficiency plays a crucial role in meeting the European Union’s Green Deal objectives and climate targets. Buildings are among the largest contributors to energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions in Europe. Improving their energy performance is essential not only for reducing emissions and achieving climate neutrality but also for tackling energy poverty—a persistent issue across the EU. [Survey data, analysis conducted for the identification of EP hotspots and the assessment of vulnerable consumers’ capacity needs](#) and [State-of-the-art review and assessment report](#) about situation the four pilot areas Brezovo (Bulgaria), Coimbra (Portugal), Riga (Latvia), and the Athens Urban Area (Greece) under the REVERTER project confirms that poor insulation, outdated heating systems, and a lack of energy efficiency measures are widespread and directly linked to financial stress, health concerns, and reduced quality of life.

However, **homeowners face numerous barriers** in accessing renovation resources and making informed decisions. These include:

- **Lack of awareness** about available subsidies or renovation programs.
- **Complex bureaucratic procedures** and administrative burdens that discourage participation, especially in low-income or aging populations.
- **Financial constraints**, with many households prioritizing short-term needs over long-term efficiency upgrades.
- **Low energy literacy** and limited understanding of energy consumption, efficiency technologies, and available support.
- **Technical and organizational challenges** in multi-family dwellings, where renovation requires collective decision-making (particularly in Latvia and Greece).

The **Digital One-Stop Shops (DOSS)** (*Figure 1*) developed by the REVERTER project offer a powerful, scalable solution to help overcome these challenges. Designed as localized digital platforms, DOSS act as centralized hubs of information and support tailored to the needs of energy-vulnerable households. They provide:

- Clear guidance on available renovation options, financial incentives, and support schemes.
- Easy access to energy calculators, contractor directories, and educational content in local languages.
- Tools to overcome behavioural and informational barriers by simplifying the renovation journey.
- Access to direct assistance – contact information of OSS personnel
- Updates about activities implemented in the area where every citizen can participate.

By integrating technical knowledge, local insights, and user-centered design, DOSS help demystify the renovation process and empower households to take action. Combined with offline support from trained REVERTER Ambassadors and local institutions, these platforms ensure a holistic approach to energy renovation—supporting climate goals while addressing the real-life needs of citizens.

Figure 1 - The four REVERTER DOSS

2. The REVERTER project overview

The REVERTER project has received funding from the European Union's LIFE programme under grant agreement No 101076277. The REVERTER stands for Deep **RE**novation roadmaps to decrease households **VulnER**ability To **En**ergy pove**R**ty. The project duration was 36 months with the kick-off in November 2022.

The **main objective** of the REVERTER project is to reduce energy poverty in Europe by equipping homeowners, tenants and landlords with comprehensive information and realistic, tailored renovation solutions.

To achieve this, the project conducts in-depth analyses of energy poverty characteristics in four pilot regions—Brezovo (Bulgaria), Coimbra (Portugal), Riga (Latvia), and the Athens Urban Area (Greece)—ensuring that solutions match the specific needs and capabilities of local households. These analyses will inform the development of nine renovation roadmaps designed to guide effective energy upgrades.

REVERTER also prioritises community engagement and capacity building. Through awareness campaigns, household consultations and targeted training, the project aims to improve comfort levels and reduce energy costs for vulnerable citizens. A key feature is the establishment of both on-site and digital One-Stop Shops (DOSS) in each pilot, acting as centralized support hubs.

Finally, the project is designed for scalability and replication. The outcomes and methodologies developed through REVERTER will be shared and promoted to encourage adoption in other municipalities across the pilot countries and the broader EU, thereby extending the impact beyond the initial target areas.

2.1. Target audiences

Diversity and common challenges across the four pilots

The four REVERTER pilot regions present distinct local conditions shaped by differences in climate, building typologies, socioeconomic contexts, and energy infrastructure. For example, Brezovo features predominantly rural, detached, and pre-1949 homes with solid fuel heating, while Coimbra and Athens are more urban, with mid-century apartment blocks that lack modern insulation. Riga is characterized by Soviet-era multi-apartment buildings with communal challenges in energy decision-making.

Detailed description about the target groups – situation in pilots can be found within the [State-of-the-art review and assessment report](#).

Despite these differences, several common elements unite the energy-vulnerable households across all four regions.

What defined target groups have in common

Low or fixed incomes

Targeted households in all pilots struggle with limited financial resources, whether due to unemployment, pension-based income, or broader economic pressures—making energy upgrades unaffordable without support.

Energy-inefficient dwellings

Buildings across all regions are largely outdated, poorly insulated, and often reliant on inefficient heating systems, leading to high energy costs and discomfort during extreme temperatures.

Limited awareness and access to support

A major barrier is that many people simply don't know that support exists. Even when subsidy programs are available, they are often unknown to those who need them most, or perceived as too complex and bureaucratic to navigate.

Health and comfort impacts

Energy poverty symptoms, such as inadequate heating, dampness, and poor air quality, are affecting the health of residents, particularly the elderly, young children, and those with pre-existing conditions.

Need for tailored solutions

What these households need are simple, easy-to-understand tools and guidance that clearly explain what support is available and how to access it. Solutions must be designed with the user in mind—clear, accessible, and localized—to help people take the first steps toward improving their homes.

2.2. The role of Digital One-Stop-Shops in the project

Within the REVERTER project, the Digital One-Stop Shops (DOSS) were designed to play a central role in facilitating access to information and supporting vulnerable households in navigating the often-complex path toward energy renovation. Their primary function is to serve as a centralized, user-friendly platform where individuals can easily find guidance, resources, and access to consultations.

The DOSS were developed to raise awareness, compile relevant information in one accessible location, and ensure that this support is available 24/7 to all internet users, not just those directly identified as vulnerable. By being open to a wider audience, the DOSS increase the chance that trusted individuals—such as family members, neighbours, or local actors—will also encounter and share helpful information, indirectly supporting those who may be less digitally literate or less proactive in seeking help.

Importantly, the DOSS do not operate in isolation. They are meant to complement the on-site (physical) One-Stop Shops (POSS), creating a synergy between digital and in-person support. While the digital platform offers constant access to essential information and tools, the POSS provide personalized advice, deeper consultation, and human interaction where needed. This combined approach makes the flow of information more efficient and inclusive, ensuring that no household is left behind in the journey toward improved energy efficiency and living conditions.

The DOSS serve as a permanent, scalable, and supportive layer of the REVERTER project's mission—helping households access what they need, when they need it, and in a way that fits their individual circumstances. A very important aspect of the DOSS was the localization of domain name, content, features and communication activities.

3. Concept and Design of Digital One-Stop Shops

The core concept of the Digital One-Stop-Shops (DOSS) was consistent across all 4 pilot countries: to serve as a central information hub for end users—primarily citizens—seeking guidance on energy efficiency, renovation schemes and other related topics and tools. While the overarching structure remained the same, each DOSS featured tailored content and functionalities specific to the needs and context of its country. Notably, the content was adapted—not merely translated—to ensure relevance and usability for local audiences.

3.1. Functionalities and evolution

As the REVERTER project progressed, the DOSS platforms evolved in parallel. Regular updates, such as news and announcements, were managed by OSS personnel, while more substantial content—like information on support schemes and tools—was updated as necessary to reflect the latest developments.

New functionalities and resources were integrated into the DOSS platforms as they became available, including links to tools such as *REVERTERup!* and the *REVERTER Atlas*.

Functionalities and features

Figure 2 illustrates the features of the 4 DOSS that were developed at the launch and later added during the project.

At launch of the digital OSS:

1. Information on DOSS - What a DOSS is: features, functionality, and goals.
2. User-centered design principles applied (e.g., accessibility, multilingual support).
3. Key digital tools or technologies used (e.g., decision support systems, energy calculators, local contractor directories, etc.).

4. Summary of all financial schemes in the specific area
5. News & Updates
6. Contacts – OSS personnel
7. Energy Ambassadors
8. Tools – developed by other projects and initiatives

Added functionalities

- Energy saving tips
- REVERTERup!
- Replication – aimed at municipalities & stakeholders
- REVERTER Atlas - aimed at municipalities & stakeholders
- Most of the other sections were updated

Figure 2 - Content and functionalities of REVERTER DOSS

Design and style

The design of the DOSS was developed in alignment with the overall REVERTER project’s visual identity to ensure a cohesive appearance and build user trust. The dominant use of green reflects the project's focus on green energy and environmental balance. A light background was selected to maintain visual clarity and simplicity, supporting ease of use. Design elements were intentionally kept minimal and intuitive, making the platform accessible and user-friendly for a broad audience.

3.2. Updates of DOSS

The development of the DOSS was carried out by WIT Berry, who also created a comprehensive user manual and conducted an online training session to introduce the main functionalities of the DOSS administration panel. The platform was built using *WordPress* in combination with *Elementor*, a user-friendly visual editor that simplifies content management and makes the administrative interface intuitive and accessible. OSS personnel received hands-on instruction on how to update and manage content. The training covered key aspects such as SEO best practices, proper image renaming and resizing, and compliance with technical standards to maintain quality and consistency across the site. This approach ensured that staff were well-equipped to manage content updates during the project and could independently maintain the platform beyond its conclusion.

3.3. Search Engine and Artificial Intelligence Optimisation

Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) and Artificial Intelligence Optimisation (AIO) were key strategic considerations in the website planning process. A comprehensive keyword analysis was conducted at the very beginning of the project to identify the focus keywords for optimisation. The main purpose of the SEO and AIO is to ensure the findability of the DOSS when users are looking for information on Google or other search engines or with a help of the Artificial Intelligence, for example Chat GPT.

Based on these findings, a tailored content strategy was implemented — covering the website's structure, textual content, image and graphic titles, meta descriptions, and title tags. The WIT team conducted regular keyword monitoring to track performance and identify trends or changes.

New content was then developed and added in response to the insights gained. The results of the SEO and AIO activities are presented for each DOSS in Section 4.

4. Country-specific Implementation

The REVERTER project followed a common communication and dissemination strategy and approach to ensure coherence and alignment across all partners. At the same time, specific activities, messages, and content were adapted at pilot level to reflect local cultural contexts and language needs. As a result, the campaigns and activities carried out in the different pilots and One-Stop-Shops (OSS) varied from country to country, ensuring that communication was both consistent at project level and effective at local level.

Latvia

Domain: www.renove.lv

Domain name means “renovate” which is easy to remember and also contributes to the SEO as it already is a keyword itself.

From day one, the Latvian DOSS included an integrated feature for users to register for online consultations. This functionality proved highly effective, with more than 500 online consultations submitted over the course of the project from July 2023 until August 2025. Notably, online consultations were already available prior to the launch of the DOSS in Riga, allowing the POSS personnel to assess the impact of the platform. Since the introduction of the DOSS, the number of consultations has increased by approximately 40%.

To raise awareness of the project and promote the DOSS, the Riga Energy Agency (REA) launched a targeted communication campaign. Posters and banners were prominently displayed in various locations across Riga, including public transport and surrounding areas. This campaign significantly boosted traffic to the DOSS and ensured that residents received information on energy poverty and potential solutions.

The communication campaign (October, 2024)

The communication campaign in Riga, Latvia included:

- Posters in public transport (rationale - vulnerable people are more likely to take public transport).
- Online (Google Ads and Facebook)
- Press releases
- Participation in TV programmes
- Events – both online and in-person (seminars, aimed both at vulnerable households, stakeholders and policy-makers)

Other communication campaigns included:

- Participation in events (exhibitions on the house renovation in Riga)
- Organizing events aimed at people living in specific area (guided tours to renovated buildings)

Figure 3 - Activities implemented in Riga, Latvia to promote DOSS & OSS

SEO and AIO

The main focus keywords for SEO are demonstrated in the table in Latvian with translations provided in English. It is important to note that Renove.lv was also findable with other keywords. The table demonstrates the improvements of the results from November 2023 until August 2025. By keeping the website up-to-date, the results should also improve in the future, ensuring the smooth continuation of the DOSS and effective exploitation of the REVERTER project's achievements. The SEO was ensured by improving the content, ensuring that the websites comply with the best practice SEO and regular content updates.

Latvia	Nov-2023	Mar-24	Aug-24	Aug-25
ēku renovācija (Building renovation)	4	3	1	1
ēkas atjaunošana (Building insulation)	6	8	7	4
Altum ēku siltināšana Rīga (Altum building insulation)	0	38	15	5
vienkāršā renovācija Rīgā (Simplified building renovation)	0	0	15	13
ēkas energoefektivitāte Rīga (building energy efficiency Riga)	31	4	3	5
kas ir energoefektivitāte Rīga (what is energy efficiency in Riga)	35	7	6	5
ēku renovācija Rīga (building renovation Riga)	8	2	2	1
ēkas atjaunošana Rīga (renovation of the building in Riga)	21	4	5	2

In addition, the findability of information was tested using ChatGPT. A query was made regarding home renovation and available information sources on this topic. The results were very positive: alongside references to the **REA**, the tool also highlighted **renove.lv** as a relevant information source (see *Figure 4*).

Figure 4 - Chat GTP results - renove.lv

Communication campaigns play a significant role in raising awareness and driving new traffic. Compared to other DOSS, Renove.lv has acquired the most visits and impressions as well as interactions via DOSS, here in a form of applications for consultations. By investing in awareness-raising efforts, such as paid media and large-scale outreach, it's possible to generate new leads and prompt attention from people who might not have otherwise considered renovation or energy efficiency. In the absence of these campaigns, the strategy relies heavily on existing interest and search behaviour. Therefore, combining consistent content efforts with periodic, targeted campaigns is the most effective approach to ensure both sustained engagement and growth in awareness.

Summary of the DOSS main statistics

Figure 5 - Main statistics about DOSS in Latvia

This matter was important in the context of the DOSS in Riga, Latvia as the pilot area has lots of buildings that require renovation in various areas of Riga. While targeting vulnerable people was the main goal of these campaigns, the project and the society in the pilot area benefited much wider from these campaign activities and information provided, disseminated and communicated in the context of REVERTER project.

In the context of Riga's pilot social media communication did not play an important role. Social media channel on Facebook was established and communication was implemented, however, it was not the main pillar of these activities. Paid search and display ads played an important role as they targeted those who are already interested in the topic, by directing them to renovē.lv.

Most visited pages on renovē.lv (Riga DOSS):

1. Forms and schemes of support
2. General information on renovation
3. The process of renovation
4. About us
5. News and Updates
6. Contact information
7. Documentation – forms, templates for renovation process
8. Useful tools and resources
9. How to become an energy ambassador
10. Useful – tools and information about renovation and energy efficiency

Main conclusions based on statistics and performance of the [renove.lv](https://www.renovate.lv)

C1. Strong demand for practical, actionable information

Pages like *Forms and schemes of support*, *Documentation – forms, templates*, and *Useful tools/resources* are among the most visited. This shows users primarily come with concrete renovation needs and want ready-to-use materials (applications, forms, financial support info).

C2. High interest in financial support and procedures

The *Forms and schemes of support* and *Process of renovation* pages being at the top suggest that funding and step-by-step guidance are the main drivers of engagement.

C3. Need for clarity and trust-building

General information on renovation, *About us*, and *Contact information* being in the top 10 shows that users also seek basic explanations, reassurance about the organisation, and easy ways to get in touch. Transparency and credibility are important to the audience.

C4. Ongoing relevance of updates and news

News and Updates being popular indicates that visitors want to stay informed about new calls, policy changes, and deadlines.

C5. Community and outreach dimension

How to become an energy ambassador ranks in the top 10, suggesting there is interest in active involvement and peer-to-peer outreach, not just passive consumption of information.

C6. Online consultations are a key driver of engagement and impact

The 40% increase in consultation requests after the launch of the DOSS shows that having a centralised, accessible platform significantly lowers barriers for households seeking guidance. This proves that digital features directly translate into measurable uptake of renovation support.

C7. Offline outreach remains essential for reaching vulnerable groups

Posters in public transport and guided tours to renovated buildings effectively targeted households who might not actively search for information online. This shows that a multi-

channel approach, combining offline and online efforts, is necessary to engage harder-to-reach groups and ensure inclusivity.

C8. The importance of SEO and AIO in enhancing digital visibility

Effective Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) and Artificial Intelligence Optimisation (AIO) are essential for ensuring that digital resources are easily discoverable by people searching for relevant information. Both the technical setup and website development play a crucial role, but equal importance lies in the relevance and quality of the content provided. Aligning website structure, design, and content with SEO and AIO best practices helps reach the intended target audiences, enhances visibility, and ensures long-term accessibility and impact of the digital platform.

Greece

Domain: www.energeiakistegi.gr

The Greek word "**Ενεργειακή Στέγη**" (**energeiakí stégi**) translates to "**Energy Roof**" or more contextually, "**Energy Shelter**" or "**Energy Housing**" in English.

- **Ενεργειακή (energeiakí)** = "energy-related" or "energetic"
- **Στέγη (stégi)** = "roof" or "shelter" (can also imply "home" or "housing" in broader terms)

In Greece, "**Ενεργειακή Στέγη**" is often used in the context of government programs or initiatives aimed at improving energy efficiency in households, such as subsidizing solar panels or home insulation. It can also refer to a specific subsidy scheme or project name focused on energy upgrades for homes. Thus, the domain name was also successfully chosen and is itself an important keyword phrase, relevant to the project and target audiences.

The main sections and content strategy of the Greek DOSS closely mirrored those of the Latvian DOSS, ensuring consistency in overall structure and user experience. However, specific sections—such as subsidy schemes, tools, and resources—were carefully adapted to reflect local needs, regulatory frameworks, and available support mechanisms in Greece. This localization ensured that the content remained relevant and practical for the target audience, while maintaining alignment with the broader goals of the REVERTER project.

The DOSS personnel in Greece were particularly active in maintaining the "News and Updates" section, regularly publishing information about upcoming and past events. This consistent content creation not only kept the audience informed but also positively

contributed to the platform’s SEO performance by incorporating relevant keywords and ensuring a steady flow of fresh content. This effort is especially important in the Athens region, where competition for top search engine rankings is significantly higher compared to Riga due to the larger population and greater number of related initiatives. As a result, achieving similar visibility in Athens requires more strategic and sustained SEO efforts.

Unlike the Latvian OSS, the Greek DOSS did not offer a direct online consultation submission form. Instead, they implemented an online application system specifically for scheduling visits from Energy Ambassadors to users' homes. This approach allowed end users to express interest and request support through a simple digital process. In total, 9 online applications were submitted, demonstrating a level of digital engagement and interest in personalized, at-home support services.

Figure 6 - Activities in Athens, Greece to promote DOSS & OSS

The specific DOSS adopted a distinct communication strategy, placing primary emphasis on media relations and public relations activities. Several press releases were distributed to media outlets and successfully published, helping to build visibility and credibility. Additionally, the POSS personnel actively participated in TV and radio programs, using these platforms to raise awareness about energy efficiency, share information about the REVERTER project’s solutions, and encourage the public to visit both the digital and POSS once they were established. Social media communication was also maintained—primarily through Facebook, which was strategically chosen as it is the most widely used platform among the project's key target group: vulnerable households in Athens, Greece.

A dedicated communication campaign was implemented on Facebook as the primary social media that the target audience uses and on Google.

SEO and AIO

In the case of the Greek pilot and DOSS, the situation proved to be more complex. The Athens area is significantly larger than Riga, resulting in greater competition and a much higher population density. Moreover, Greece already had several well-established online resources on similar topics, making it more challenging to achieve high rankings in Google search results. Despite that, the data demonstrates that approximately 30% of all traffic sources is Organic search.

To address this challenge, **EKPIZO**, the organisation responsible for the DOSS operations in Greece, implemented a proactive strategy that included regular content updates, enhanced media communication, and strengthening its overall digital presence. These efforts helped improve visibility and ensure that the DOSS platform reached its target audiences more effectively.

Taking these factors into consideration, continuous communication and regular optimisation of the DOSS are essential to achieving and maintaining strong results.

Summary of the DOSS main statistics

Figure 7 - Main statistics about DOSS in Greece

Most visited landing pages on Energeiakistegi.gr

1. Renovation process explained in 3 steps
2. General information on energy efficiency and renovation
3. Information on benefits of building renovation
4. How does energy upgrade work?
5. News and updates
6. Information on a new programme “I Save 2025” – support for citizens
7. About OSS
8. Information on various support programmes for citizens
9. Useful tools – landing page with links and info on other useful tools
10. Contact information

Main conclusions based on statistics and performance of the Energeiakistegi.gr

C1. Consistency with flexibility works well

By mirroring the main structure of the Latvian DOSS while adapting subsidy schemes, tools, and resources to the Greek regulatory and cultural context, the Greek DOSS achieved both **alignment with REVERTER goals** and **local relevance**. This shows the value of a **shared framework with local customization** while saving effort and money from repeating the same fork again.

C2. News and SEO-driven content are critical in competitive contexts

The Greek team’s active maintenance of the *News and Updates* section improved SEO and visibility, which is especially important in Athens, where **competition for online visibility is much stronger** than in Riga. This demonstrates that **regular content updates and keyword-rich posts are key to sustaining reach in larger markets**.

C3. Media and public relations boosted credibility

Active use of **press releases, TV, and radio appearances** helped build **trust and visibility** among the general public, complementing digital outreach. This was especially important in Greece, where **traditional media channels remain highly influential**.

C4. Users seek simple, step-by-step guidance

The most visited page, *Renovation process explained in 3 steps*, shows that people want **clear, straightforward explanations** of how to start and complete renovation, rather than complex technical details.

C5. Practical and financial benefits drive interest

Pages on *benefits of building renovation* and *support programmes (incl. "I Save 2025")* are highly ranked, confirming that households are primarily motivated by **economic support opportunities** and **visible personal gains**.

C6. General knowledge and awareness are also important

Strong traffic to *General information on energy efficiency and renovation* and *How does energy upgrade work?* indicates that many users still need **basic awareness-raising content** to understand why renovation matters.

C7. Trust and transparency support engagement

Visits to *About OSS* and *Contact information* highlight that users also want to know **who provides the information** and have **direct contact points**, which builds confidence in the platform

C8. More effort required: SEO and AIO challenges in competitive digital environments

Based on the results and insights from the SEO and AIO implementation for the Greek DOSS, several important conclusions can be drawn. The Greek pilot faced unique challenges compared to other countries due to the larger and more competitive digital environment in the Athens area and the presence of several well-established online resources. As a result, achieving high visibility and top Google search rankings required more time and consistent effort.

The experience demonstrates that effective communication and continuous optimisation are essential for maintaining and improving online visibility in competitive environments. Sustained attention to both the technical and content-related aspects of SEO and AIO ensures that the DOSS continues to reach citizens effectively and remains a trusted and accessible resource for home renovation information.

Bulgaria

Domain: <https://reverter-brezovo.bg/>

The structure was similar to the other REVERTER DOSS and the main differences were in the content and specifically the renovation schemes as well as the tools. Bulgaria’s DOSS did not have an online consultation form. It invited people to send their questions so that they could advise them via phone or e-mail response. In total 4 questions were received.

As the municipality is relatively small, the main communication and raising awareness activities included the local events and dissemination activities of the municipality of Brezovo. No dedicated communication campaigns were implemented. In Brezovo municipality the DOSS played a significantly smaller role than in Riga or Athens.

Figure 8 - Activities implemented in Bulgaria to promote DOSS & OSS

The main traffic source is “Direct” which is directly linked to the events and activities implemented in the Municipality as large number of visitors most likely searched for additional information online.

SEO and AIO

Some of the keywords that were the main focus in Brezovo, Bulgaria are listed below in the table. The unique context of Brezovo enabled the local DOSS to achieve high rankings in both Google search results and AI-based queries. The main advantage, compared to other DOSS

locations, lies in the smaller population size and the limited number of similar digital resources available in the region, resulting in lower competition.

Consequently, even though the Brezovo DOSS was not updated frequently, it still achieved strong visibility and good results due to the favourable digital landscape and reduced competition.

Bulgaria - keywords	Nov-23	Mar-24	Aug-24	Feb-25	Aug-25
саниране на сгради Брезово (building renovation Brezovo)	1	3	3	2	6
кандидатстване по програма енергийна ефективност Брезово (applying for the Brezovo energy efficiency program)	1	1	1	1	1
фонд енергийна ефективност Брезово (Energy Efficiency Fund Brezovo)	2	2	2	3	1
енергийно обновяване на българските домове Брезово (Energy renovation of Bulgarian homes Brezovo)	1	1	1	1	1
пестене на енергия Брезово (energy saving Brezovo)	1	1	1	1	1
инициативи за пестене на енергия Брезово (energy saving initiatives Brezovo)	0	1	1	1	1
пестене на електрическа енергия Брезово (saving electricity Brezovo)	0	1	1	1	7
пестене на енергия проект Брезово (energy saving project Brezovo)	0	1	1	1	1
зелена енергия Брезово (green energy Brezovo)	3	4	3	2	1
европейски програми за зелена енергия Брезово (European green energy programs Brezovo)	1	1	1	1	1
енергоспестяване Брезово (energy saving Brezovo)	2	10	0	1	1
пестене на енергия (energy saving)	0	28	25	11	8
инициативи за пестене на енергия (energy saving initiatives)	0	0	39	27	7

The Chat GPT results are illustrated in *Figure 9*. They demonstrate that in this area, the first results that people would consult would be reverter-brezovo.bg.

Figure 9 - reverter-brezovo.bg results for Chat GPT

Summary of the DOSS main statistics

Figure 10 - Main statistics about DOSS in Bulgaria

The visitors of this DOSS were most interested in the information on:

1. News and Updates
2. About the DOSS
3. The process of renovation – the steps to take from application to renovated building
4. Energy efficiency – Renovation section
5. Energy saving tips
6. OSS contact information
7. Energy Ambassadors
8. Questions and Answers
9. How REVERTER OSS can help you
10. Useful information – hosting various links and tools to REVERTER and other resources

Main conclusions based on statistics and performance of the Reverter-brezovo.bg

C1. Limited communication campaigns

Unlike Riga or Athens, the Brezovo DOSS relied mainly on local events and municipal dissemination activities, without implementing dedicated communication campaigns. This explains its smaller role and relatively modest reach.

C2. High direct traffic indicates local event impact

The fact that 56% of traffic came from direct searches suggests that awareness was raised mainly through offline activities, where participants later sought more information online.

C3. Modest engagement through questions

Since no online consultation form was available, residents had to submit questions via phone or e-mail. Only 4 questions were received, showing limited direct interaction compared to other DOSS platforms. This might also be linked to a proportion of those who visit the website and ask questions. Thus, the smaller number of visitors, fewer interactions.

C4. Content interest focused on practical guidance

Visitors were primarily drawn to practical and actionable information, such as renovation steps, energy efficiency, and saving tips, showing that users seek guidance for concrete renovation actions.

C5. Desktop as the main access device

With 78% of visits coming from desktop computers, the platform's audience appears to be less mobile-oriented, possibly reflecting the older demographics of a small municipality.

C6. Organic search and social media play secondary roles

Organic search (32%) and social media (7%) contributed to traffic but were less significant, reinforcing that direct outreach and municipal events were the main drivers of engagement.

C7. Relatively small reach but valuable for awareness

Despite generating only about 1.5K impressions and 7 publications, the DOSS served as an important awareness-raising tool in Brezovo, offering access to renovation-related information and centralizing resources for the local community.

C8. Low competition drives strong SEO and AIO results

The Brezovo DOSS case shows that lower competition and fewer digital resources in the region contributed to high SEO and AIO performance, even with limited website updates. However, to maintain visibility and relevance over time, regular optimisation and content updates remain essential.

Portugal

Domain: <https://renovar.coimbra.pt/>

The Portuguese DOSS was created as subdomain of the city's official website Coimbra.pt. The "renovar" in Portuguese means renovate which is easy to understand and remember. It is also one of the keywords that is relevant to the project and DOSS activities and purpose.

Having a common structure to other DOSS, again the main differences were in the content and specifically renovation schemes as well as the tools. Portuguese DOSS did not have an online consultation form. It invited people to send their questions so that they could advise them via phone or e-mail. In total 3 questions were received.

Figure 11 - Activities implemented in Portugal to promote DOSS & OSS

The target audience of the Portuguese pilot was very specific and narrow. Thus, no large-scale communication campaigns were organized. The DOSS relied mainly on local events and information disseminated by the Municipality of Coimbra. Also, various publications were made on behalf of Municipality – on their website.

SEO and AIO

The Coimbra DOSS operates in a region with a relatively small population and a very specific, well-defined target audience. Despite these factors, ensuring that the platform was easily findable online remained an important objective. Even though the website content was not frequently updated, the DOSS was developed following best SEO practices, which enabled it to achieve strong Google rankings and maintain good visibility for relevant keywords.

Moreover, AI-based search analysis confirmed that, within this region, alongside the Coimbra Municipality's Renovar.coimbra.pt, the DOSS is recognised as a reliable and trustworthy information source (See Table and Figure 12).

Portugal - keywords	23-Nov	Mar-24	Aug-24	Feb-25	Aug-25
renovação energética (energy renewal)	0	28	21	16	16
vale eficiência energética Coimbra (energy efficiency voucher Coimbra)	10	2	8	12	5
voucher eficiência energética Coimbra (energy efficiency voucher Coimbra)	0	2	2	5	14
fundo de eficiência energética Coimbra (Coimbra Energy Efficiency Fund)	0	3	4	6	6

eficiência energética Coimbra (energy efficiency Coimbra)	0	31	7	18	4
financiamento eficiência energética Coimbra (energy efficiency financing in Coimbra)	4	1	1	1	1
vale de eficiência energética Coimbra (Coimbra Energy Efficiency Valley)	0	2	5	9	2
comunidades de Energia Coimbra (Coimbra Energy Communities)	32	10	12	10	8
melhoria do desempenho energético Coimbra (improving energy performance in Coimbra)	0	3	6	3	1
reabilitação energética Coimbra (energy rehabilitation in Coimbra)	0	4	1	1	1
renovação energética Coimbra (energy renewal in Coimbra)	1	1	1	1	1
Financiamento Eficiência Energética Coimbra (Energy Efficiency Financing Coimbra)	0	1	1	1	1

The Chat GPT provide renovar.coimbra.pt as one of the key resources for information.

Figure 12 - Results for renovar.coimbra.pt for Chat GPT

Summary of the DOSS main statistics

Figure 13 - Main statistics about DOSS in Portugal

The visitors of this DOSS were most interested in the information on:

1. Renovation – process and support possibilities
2. Ask a question – application form
3. About OSS
4. Building renovation
5. News – information about the REVERTER project and its goals
6. Contact information
7. Events and updates
8. Energy ambassadors
9. Building renovation – the process and steps to take
10. Useful information and tools – links to other tools, publications and projects

Main conclusions based on statistics and performance of the [Renovar.coimbra.pt](http://renovar.coimbra.pt)

C1. Integration with the City's website boosted accessibility

Hosting the DOSS as a subdomain of Coimbra's official website (coimbra.pt) likely enhanced visibility and trustworthiness, while the clear and relevant keyword "renovar" made it easy to understand and remember.

C2. Niche target audience and limited campaigns

Since the DOSS was aimed at a very specific and narrow target group, no large-scale communication campaigns were organized. Instead, promotion relied mainly on local events and publications by the Municipality of Coimbra.

C3. High direct traffic suggests effective local promotion during events

With 73.4% of traffic being direct, it is clear that local dissemination activities and municipal publications effectively guided users straight to the platform, rather than through search engines or social media.

C4. Low engagement via questions

Similar to Bulgaria, the Portuguese DOSS did not feature an online consultation form. Instead, it relied on phone and e-mail communication, which resulted in only 3 submitted questions, indicating relatively low user interaction.

C5. Content interest focused on renovation guidance

Visitors were most engaged with practical content such as renovation processes, support opportunities, building renovation steps, and useful tools. This reflects a demand for concrete, actionable guidance.

C6. Desktop as the primary access point

Most users (76.76%) accessed the DOSS via desktop computers, with smartphones at 22.92% and minimal tablet usage. This suggests the platform was mostly used in a formal, research-oriented context rather than casual browsing.

C7. Moderate reach with strong municipal backing

With over 4.5K impressions and 6 publications, the Portuguese DOSS achieved a moderate reach compared to other pilots. Its strength lay in being backed by the municipality's official channels, ensuring credibility and alignment with local communication.

C8. Strong SEO foundations ensure visibility in a very specific area

The Coimbra DOSS demonstrates that even in regions with a small population and a narrow target audience, applying solid SEO principles can ensure good online visibility. Although content updates were infrequent, the DOSS's technical optimisation and targeted keywords enabled it to remain easily discoverable and recognised—both by search engines and AI tools—as a trustworthy local information source.

5. User Engagement and communication strategies

Section 5 described individual communication activities in each pilot. This section provides summary of all activities.

Activity	Latvia	Greece	Bulgaria	Portugal
Press releases	4 sent 4 published	6 sent 126 published	5 sent 10 published	9 sent 7 published
Social media	Communication only about events > 30 posts > 70 k views	Active communication > 40 posts > 160 k views	Posts on the Municipality social media 9 posts > 2 k views	Posts on the Municipality social media > 70 posts > 14 k views
Campaigns	Integrated marketing campaign: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Displays • Public transport • AdWords • Social media • Participation to 2 exhibitions 	Online campaign: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AdWords • Facebook 	No additional campaigns	No additional campaigns
Social events	10 social events with more than 300 participants	8 social events with more than 270 participants	6 social events with more than 263 participants	6 social events with more than 205 participants
Educational events	0	3 with more than 280 participants	1 with more than 30 participants	1 with more than 50 participants
Other	Radio interview TV interview	Radio interview TV interview	No other activities	No other activities
Printed materials	Flyers with QR codes, links to DOSS and energy saving tips			
Videos (promo videos on how OSS works)	1 published on DOSS and social media	2 published on DOSS and social media	2 published on DOSS and social media	1 published on DOSS and social media
SEO	Updates	Active updates	Passive updates	Passive updates

6. Challenges and lessons learned

The implementation of Digital One-Stop Shops (DOSS) across the REVERTER pilot countries offered valuable insights into what makes such platforms effective in addressing energy poverty. While each context presented its own challenges, several common lessons emerged from the project experience.

1. Human commitment and visibility are essential

A key takeaway is that the success of a DOSS is closely tied to the **level of engagement and effort** invested by the local DOSS personnel. Platforms that were actively maintained, regularly updated, and supported by communication efforts—such as those in Riga and Athens—saw significantly higher traffic and user engagement. This underscores that technology alone is not enough; **human commitment and visibility are essential**.

2. Targeted awareness campaigns are critical

Even when a DOSS is well-optimized for search engines, targeted awareness campaigns **remain critical**. Many individuals experiencing energy poverty do not actively seek information online. Campaigns—especially those using posters, digital ads, and public transport banners—are effective in reaching these harder-to-reach groups. The Riga and Athens pilots demonstrated that such outreach dramatically increases visibility and use.

3. Ease the access to information and interaction with professionals in various ways

Interactive tools, like online consultation request forms, proved to be more effective than static contact options. In Latvia, many users were more willing to schedule a consultation than send a question, indicating a preference for structured, action-oriented interaction over open-ended inquiries.

4. Importance of regular updates

Regularly updating the website content—especially news, events, and support scheme changes—had a dual benefit: it kept users informed and improved search engine ranking. This was particularly important in high-competition areas like Athens, where sustained SEO efforts were necessary to maintain visibility.

5. Social media remains an important communication channel

Social media activity, while not a primary traffic driver in all contexts, provided an important channel for reaching interested audiences and sharing timely updates. Facebook, in particular, proved effective in Greece, where it aligns with the usage patterns of vulnerable populations.

6. Choosing right channels for campaigns is crucial

Campaigns that used context-aware targeting—like placing advertisements in spaces frequented by vulnerable populations (e.g., public transport)—had higher impact. This shows that thoughtful placement, not just volume of advertising, determines success in awareness-raising.

7. Localisation of the content

Localization of the content was essential for credibility and user engagement. Simply translating content was not sufficient—DOSS that adapted tools, language, and subsidy information to local needs, such as in Greece and Bulgaria, saw higher relevance and usefulness.

8. Media relations

Media relations—including TV and radio appearances—played a key role in building trust and extending reach beyond digital channels, particularly among older or less digitally connected populations.

9. User-centric design of digital platforms

Simplicity and intuitive navigation boosted engagement. DOSS that presented information in clear, user-friendly formats saw higher user satisfaction and return visits.

10. Domain name

Domain names that included relevant keywords, such as *renove.lv* or *energeiakistegi.gr*, not only made the platforms more memorable but also enhanced SEO performance from the outset.

11. Independent update of the content by OSS personnel

Training local DOSS personnel on digital tools, SEO, and content management (as done by WIT Berry) supported the long-term sustainability of each platform, ensuring knowledge retention beyond the project lifecycle. When establishing DOSS, it is essential that there is one person in each POSS that is familiar with the content management system and can update the DOSS, not only publish news and updates, but also make changes in other sections such as subsidy schemes, documents, for example, as the statistics demonstrate that those sections are the most visited and of crucial importance to the end users.

12. Awareness and engagement campaigns need to be adapted to each area

In smaller or less digitally connected communities, like Brezovo, relying solely on digital tools was not enough. Offline outreach and municipal engagement were necessary to ensure inclusiveness. For example, it is possible that such campaigns as radio or posters on buses would not be cost-effective in areas as Brezovo.

13. SEO and AIO

Both Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) and Artificial Intelligence Optimisation (AIO) are essential for the success of any digital platform. With Google's continued dominance and the growing influence of AI-driven search tools, content providers must dedicate sufficient resources and strategic effort to compete effectively for online attention.

The greatest challenge lies in highly competitive digital environments—particularly in larger countries or densely populated regions—where achieving visibility requires significantly more effort to reach comparable results.

Therefore, owners, managers and operators of digital platforms should be aware of these dynamics and develop their communication and content strategies accordingly, ensuring that both technical optimisation and content relevance are continuously maintained to stay visible and impactful.

14. Monitor and improve

Finally, website analytics were an invaluable resource. Monitoring user behaviour and traffic sources helped tailor content and refine outreach strategies. Embedding such feedback mechanisms into future DOSS will enhance their responsiveness and effectiveness. The POSS personnel need to keep on monitoring the results of the DOSS regularly and adapt their communication strategies and activities as well as the content of the DOSS, accordingly.

7. Future Developments and Recommendations

As the REVERTER project concludes, ensuring the continued relevance, visibility, and usability of the Digital One-Stop Shops (DOSS) is critical to maintaining long-term impact. Based on the lessons learned, several strategic recommendations can guide post-project management of DOSS platforms:

1. Assign clear ownership and responsibility

Each DOSS should have a designated administrator or team responsible for regular content updates, user support and platform maintenance. This ensures continuity and accountability

beyond the project's lifetime. WIT Berry remains available to provide technical support to DOSS personnel as needed.

2. Maintain regular content updates

Sustained engagement and SEO performance depend on a steady flow of new content. This includes updating information on subsidy schemes, renovation policies, local events, and success stories. A minimum content calendar (e.g., quarterly updates) should be established to keep the site active and relevant.

3. Integrate DOSS into local and national strategies

To ensure policy alignment and funding continuity, DOSS should be formally integrated into existing municipal or national energy poverty mitigation programs. This might include collaboration with ministries, local authorities, and EU structural fund frameworks.

4. Continue digital outreach and targeted campaigns

Post-project, DOSS visibility must be supported through periodic awareness efforts. Even with limited budgets, targeted digital advertising (e.g., Facebook and Google Ads) and partnerships with local media can help maintain user traffic and reach new audiences.

5. Build strategic partnerships for expansion and content sharing

Municipalities, NGOs, contractors, and consumer protection groups can be valuable partners. These stakeholders can contribute content, co-promote services, or integrate DOSS into broader citizen engagement and energy transition activities.

6. Encourage offline referrals and use through local networks

In areas with lower digital literacy, community workers, local energy advisors, or REVERTER Ambassadors (or their successors) should be encouraged to introduce households to the DOSS during in-person visits or local events.

7. Monitor usage and adjust accordingly

Continue to track web analytics and user feedback to evaluate what content is most used and what improvements may be needed. This user-centric approach ensures ongoing platform relevance and usability.

8. Secure funding for long-term operation

To ensure sustainability, local authorities or DOSS operators should seek to integrate platform maintenance costs into regular operating budgets or apply for continuation funding through EU or national energy transition programmes.

9. Promote replication in other regions

The DOSS architecture and approach offer a replicable model. Sharing templates, best practices, and open-source platform elements can support other municipalities or regions in deploying similar solutions. The dedicated landing pages will remain and the project partners should remain accessible in case any municipality would like to get more information with an aim to replicate. This is already implemented during the REVERTER project.

10. Online applications

Online application forms for consultations could help create better interaction. The Riga DOSS example clearly illustrates that online application forms work. It allows people to reserve their time and be sure that the OSS professionals will pay all their attention to their needs, interests and questions.

11. SEO and AIO

To stay visible and competitive in an increasingly AI-driven digital environment, digital platform owners should adopt a long-term optimisation strategy that combines SEO and AIO principles. This means continuously monitoring performance, updating content to match user intent, and adapting to evolving algorithms. By investing in relevant, high-quality content and maintaining technical excellence, platforms can strengthen their online presence and ensure lasting visibility, even in highly competitive markets.

8. Conclusion

The most effective strategy for future DOSS development would be to implement a multi-channel communication approach, combining banners, press releases, and online campaigns to maximize outreach and impact. The budget can be strategically allocated across these channels to ensure balanced visibility. Notably, press campaigns may require no financial investment if strong relationships with media outlets have already been established.

Digital channels such as Google AdWords and Facebook campaigns are particularly valuable. AdWords can effectively capture interest at the search stage, while Facebook enables precise targeting by region, demographics, and interests, ensuring messages reach the most relevant

audiences. Effort in SEO and AIO can significantly support all communication activities and allow to invest less in any paid media.

Offline promotion remains equally important. Banners and posters in and around public transport have proven to be highly effective in raising awareness and driving traffic to the platform. However, they need to be adapted to the scale of the area. For example, one banner next to Municipality (such as Brezovo) might be sufficient. While larger areas, cities and towns such as Riga or Athens, might need a more targeted and larger campaign.

Ultimately, the success of the DOSS is directly linked to the communication activities implemented. To engage users, the DOSS must provide information that is not only practical and useful but also presented in a clear, concise and engaging format.